

The yield differences among the entries were significant in both years. DR cultivars recorded higher yields than IET or OR cultivars. DR83-1 and DR83-2 in both normal and drought years outyielded the other entries, indicating their drought tolerance capacity. □

Response of rainfed upland rice to chlormequat chloride

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Upland, rainfed rice yields in Orissa are very low because of continuous drought. The use of a growth retardant on rice may improve crop yield by enabling the plant to resist drought through root proliferation.

We studied the effect of chlormequat chloride on the grain yield of rice at the Regional Research Station, Semiliguda, in Jun-Sep 1979. The soil was a clay loam (Ochrept) with pH 5.5, 0.852% organic matter, 9.5 kg available P/ha, cation exchange capacity 8.5 meq/100 g soil, and water-holding capacity 45%. Parijat (100 d duration) and Subhadra (90 d) were the test varieties.

The crops suffered from intermittent drought at various growth stages

Table 1. Stages of growth and drought spells suffered by the crop. Semiliguda, Orissa, India, Jun-Sep 1979.

Plant age	Drought conditions
<i>Seedling</i>	
Germination to day 4	No drought
Day 5 to 19	Drought
<i>Vegetative</i>	
Day 20 to 40	No drought
Day 41 to 52	Drought
Day 53	No drought
<i>Reproductive</i>	
Day 54 to 60	Drought
Day 61 to 62	No drought
Day 63 to 68	Drought
Day 69	No drought
<i>Flowering and ripening</i>	
Day 70 until harvest	Drought

Table 2. Effect of chlormequat chloride on rice yield. Semiliguda, Orissa, India, Jun-Sep 1979.

Chlormequat chloride (ppm)	Sprays (no.)	Time of spray (d after germination)	Grain yield (t/ha)	
			Parijat	Subhadra
0 (water)	—	—	2.0	1.5
500	1	25	2.1	1.8
1000	1	25	2.2	1.8
500	2	25,40	2.4	1.9
1000	2	25,40	2.3	1.8
CD (0.05)	—	—	0.3	0.1

(Table 1). After germination, chlormequat chloride at 500 and 1,000 ppm was sprayed once or twice.

Both varieties yielded significantly

higher when 500 ppm chlormequat chloride was sprayed twice (Table 2). The response was higher in Subhadra than in Parijat. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization ADVERSE SOILS TOLERANCE

Screening for zinc deficiency tolerance in rice

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Zn deficiency is becoming a major nutritional problem limiting rice yield. Genetic variability for tolerating it exists in rice genotypes. During the 1985 wet season at Pusa, severe Zn deficiency was observed in a varietal trial of 16 entries

grown in 15-m² plots in 3 replications. The symptoms were severe 25-30 d after transplanting. The soil was a light, extremely calcareous (free CaCO₃ 39%) sandy loam (organic C 0.48%, pH 8.6, EC 0.50 dS/m).

Scoring was based on percentage of hills affected in a plot (see table). Zn content of the third leaf from the top (five leaves from each replication, bulked) was determined with an atomic absorption spectrophotometer. Tolerant varieties had higher Zn concentration in

Zinc tolerance in rice varieties. Bihar, India, 1985 wet season.

IET no.	Designation	Cross	Score ^a	Zn concentration (ppm)
3279	CR126-42-2	Dungansali/IR8	3	28
—	NC1626	Selection from land races	1	38
7614	RP1451-1712-4319	Rasi/Fine Gora	3	29
7613	RP1670-1418-2205-1582	M63-83/Cauvery	3	24
6148	TNAU6464	Bala/CO 13	3	28
7254	TNAU(AD)103	Tiruveni/Amravathi CO 3	3	27
7564	RP1667-301-1196-1562	IRAT8/N22	7	16
7616	RP1888-4259-1529-126	RP79-5/Tella Vadlu	5	22
—	IR25588-7-3-1	IR19657-37-3/IR9129-209-2-2	7	14
—	Pusa 4-11	Tadukan/IRB	7	16
—	Pusa 33	Improved Sabarmati/Ratna	7	19
—	Pusa 2-21	IR8/TKM6	7	17
—	ES29-5-3	—	9	13
—	RAU4004-127	—	9	12
6223	CR222-MW10	MTU15/Waikoku	9	13
—	IR25890-82-5-3	RP825-714-II/CR113-32// IR9129-209-2-2	9	13

^aBased on percentage of hills affected in a plot: 1 < 1%, 3 = 1-5%, 5 = 6-25%, 7 = 26-50%, 9 = 51-100%.